

A Rare Case of Ovarian Lipid Cell Tumour in a Post-Menopausal WomanShweta Sharma¹, Mansi Shrigiriwar², Manjushree Waikar³¹Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, GMCH, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, GMCH, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India³Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, GMCH, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shweta Sharma

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Post-menopausal women presenting with features of hyperandrogenism is a diagnostic challenge for clinicians. Female virilisation can be caused by androgen excess originating either from the adrenal gland or ovary. Adrenal hyperandrogenemia is caused by primary adrenal tumors, adrenocorticotrophic hormone-producing tumors such as Cushing disease, or congenital adrenal hyperplasia, while ovarian hyperandrogenism is caused by PCOS or androgen-producing tumours of the ovary. We present a rare case of Lipid cell tumour which needs to be considered in the differential diagnosis in a postmenopausal woman presenting with virilizing symptoms and highlight the importance of early diagnosis and management.

Keywords: Lipid Cell Tumour, Ovarian Hyperandrogenism, Female Virilisation.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Post-menopausal women presenting with features of hyperandrogenism is a diagnostic challenge for clinicians. Various non-tumorous and tumorous causes of ovary and adrenal gland need to be evaluated. When clinical manifestations of hirsutism are more severe and/or accompanied by virilizing symptoms like male pattern baldness, clitoromegaly, and deepening of voice, a tumorous source of excessive androgen secretion originating from either the adrenals or the ovaries should be excluded. Ovarian steroid cell tumors account for less than 0.1% of all ovarian tumors. Lipid cell tumor of the ovary belongs to a group of ovarian neoplasms whose cells are large, round, or polyhedral and are infrequently encountered ovarian neoplasms. These tumours exhibit an organoid or diffuse arrangement of large, rounded or polyhedral cells that resemble Leydig, stromal lutein, or adrenal cortical cells. It has been reported that evidence of virilisation is found in 75% of these tumours, Since they lack crystals of Rinke and their topographic features have been obliterated, they cannot be identified specifically as either type of tumour. [1] The origin of this tumour is unknown and each cell type that it resembles must be considered as a potential source. Most often, they occur in women of reproductive age, particularly during the third and fourth decades and rarely in postmenopausal women or children. [2] The majority of these tumours are hormonally active and the symptoms are related to the hypersecretion of the biologically active steroids. An increased secretion of androgens usually occurs

in approximately 50% of cases. Most of the lipid cell tumours are benign but in 20% of cases, they follow a malignant clinical course with spread within abdomen and even distant metastasis. [3]

We present a rare case of Steroid cell tumor in a postmenopausal woman presenting with virilizing symptoms.

Case History

A 67 year old diabetic, hypertensive postmenopausal female patient P3L3 presented with complaints of generalized dull aching pain abdomen, relieved on medications since 2-3 years. The pain was more in the right hypochondriac region, associated with loss of appetite and weight loss. She also had a history of excessive hair growth (hirsutism) over upper lip, chin, upper chest and abdomen and on both the breasts since 6 years and male pattern baldness since 4 years. She was a known case of chronic kidney disease with renal calculi since 2 years and had undergone right sided DJ stenting for ureteric calculi. She did not have bowel or bladder related complaints. There was also no alteration in her sleep cycles. There was no history of any exogenous hormone therapy. Obstetrics history was insignificant; she was postmenopausal since 11 years.

General Examination was unremarkable except for the presence of pallor. Hair was present on upper lip, chin, upper chest, abdomen and on both breasts. Vital parameters were normal. There were no abnormal findings on systemic Examination.

Gynecological examination revealed the presence of clitoromegaly. Per speculum examination

showed pale vagina and a bulky cervix. No vaginal discharge was present. Per vaginal

examination revealed a small, retroverted Uterus. Fornices were free and non-tender bilaterally.

Figure 1: Male pattern Hypertrophy of Clitoris

Routine blood investigations were normal except for raised Blood urea (74mg/dl) and Serum creatinine (4.7 mg/dl). Thyroid function tests were within normal limits.

The observed values and the normal limits of the hormonal levels were as shown below:

Total testosterone - 98.88 ng/dl (normal range <75)

Free testosterone – 35ng/dl (normal range:15-17)

Serum cortisol- 9.5 mcg/dl (normal range:10-20)

Serum Prolactin- 21.92 ng/ml (normal range <25)

Serum DHEAS- 32.41 mcg/dl (normal range 25-46)

FSH- 2.21 mIU/ml (normal range: 25.8-134.8)

LH- 2.48I U/ml (normal range: 14.2-52.3)

There was an increase in the Total and Free testosterone levels with normal FSH and LH levels

indicating an ovarian cause for the observed abnormal values. The values of the tumor markers were within normal range as shown below.

CA125- 37.1u/ml (normal range: 0-35)

AFP- 38 mcg/ml (normal range < 40)

CEA- 2.8 mcg/ml (normal range < 2.5)

Ultrasound examination of the abdomen showed the presence of a hypoechoic right adnexal mass measuring 2.8*2.9* 3 centimeters. Right ureteric calculi were also noted. Plain CT KUB revealed proximal right obstructive ureteric calculus with mild hydronephrosis. Further evaluation with MRI pelvis showed the presence of a neoplastic lesion of Right ovary, likely Sex cord stromal tumour of sertoli leydig cell type measuring 2.7* 2.9* 2.7 centimeters.

Patient was posted for exploratory laparotomy with Radical hystrectomy and lymph node dissection.

The excised specimen was sent for histopathological examination. On Gross examination, a well circumscribed yellowish

lesion, of size 2.5*2*1.5 centimeters was present without any capsule breach

Figure 2: Gross and cut section showing a well circumscribed yellowish lesion

Microscopy showed tumour mass composed of round to polyhedral cells with round nuclei and abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm. At places tumour cells showed clear cytoplasm separated by fibrocollagenous stroma. Mitosis was also seen,

with low rate of mitosis of 2/20 hpf. Lymphovascular invasion was not observed. These histological features were suggestive of lipid cell tumour (leydig cell tumour).

Figure 3: Immunohistochemistry Picture

Immunohistochemistry examination was positive for SF-1 and inhibin-alpha markers and also revealed features consistent with steroid cell tumour of ovary of oxyphil type.

Figure 4: Microscopic Picture

The patient was not offered any further medications or chemotherapy as it was a low grade disease and hysterectomy with bilateral salphingo-oophorectomy was deemed to be suffice.

Post-operative course was uneventful and the patient was discharged in a stable condition with advice to follow up with nephrology in view of Chronic kidney disease (CKD). At 6 months followup the patient was doing well and Testosterone levels were back to normal range.

Discussion

Ovarian steroid cell tumors account for less than 0.1% of all ovarian tumors. [4] This term applies to a group of rare tumors which are usually virilizing, characterized by endocrine type architecture and are formed of large oval polygonal cells which resemble lutein, leydig or adrenocortical cells. These tumors are derived from ovarian stromal cells, which differentiate in variety of pathways to produce a range of tumors of common histogenesis.

Adrenal and ovarian steroid producing cells are derived from common primitive mesenchymal cell. When the stromal cell in the ovary becomes neoplastic they have the potential to function like adrenocortical tissue. They form a subtype of sex-chord stromal tumors. They are usually benign and unilateral. These tumors can originate from any normal steroid hormone producing cell and hence are further divided into three subtypes: stromal leutoma, Leydig cell tumor and Steroid cell tumor (not otherwise specified).

Majority of lipid cell tumours are hormonally active and the symptoms are related to the hypersecretion of the biologically active steroids. An increased secretion of androgens usually occurs in approximately 50% of cases leading to virilisation, a condition in which a female develops male sex characteristics (eg lower pitch of voice, baldness or thicker body hair) and pelvic masses (lumps) as a result of male hormone (testosterone) production by the tumour. [5]

Clinical symptoms usually differ based on hormonal secretion and tumor progression. At early stages, most patients present with virilization signs including amenorrhea or oligomenorrhea. At later stages, more significant signs of masculinization are presented including severe hirsutism, acne, deepened voice and clitaromegaly as in our case. Also, estrogenic manifestations have been reported including endometrial hyperplasia and bleeding in postmenopausal women, and in approximately 6–10% of cases, patients might present with symptoms of Cushing's syndrome due to elevated plasma cortisol levels Other nonspecific symptoms include abdominal pain and distention, whereas patients might be asymptomatic in approximately 25% of cases. [6]

Differential diagnosis of female virilization is essential. Female virilisation can be caused by androgen excess originating either from the adrenal gland or ovary. Adrenal hyperandrogenemia is caused by primary adrenal tumors, adrenocorticotrophic hormone-producing tumors such as Cushing disease, or congenital adrenal hyperplasia. Conversely, ovarian hyperandrogenism is caused by PCOS or androgen-producing tumors of the ovary. In the present case, there were no findings of adrenal hyperandrogenism and no sign of polycystic ovary.

Ultrasonography, which is typically used in the primary evaluation of ovarian tumors, has limited sensitivity in detecting steroid cell tumors, whereas it could reveal the possibility of malignant transformation through demonstrating abnormal blood flow. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has a higher efficacy in differentiating epithelial and non-epithelial ovarian tumors including steroid cell tumors that appear as intermediate-signal intense heterogeneous solid masses. While clinical and radiological examinations provide helpful clues for establishing a primary differential diagnosis for ovarian neoplasms, confirming a specific and detailed final diagnosis depends mainly on histopathological examination. [7]

Microscopically, steroid cell tumors are characterized by a bimodal proliferation of large polygonal cells with vacuolated cytoplasm and smaller cells with abundant granular eosinophilic cytoplasm. These cells are typically arranged in a diffuse pattern or small nests within the vascular stroma. The absence of crystals or Reinke is helpful to distinguish these tumours from Leidyg cell tumors that are accompanied by Leidyg cell hyperplasia. Also, the lack of spindle cells and fibromatous background is useful to distinguish it from luteinized thecoma.

Most of the lipid cell tumours are benign but in 20% of cases, they follow a malignant clinical course with spread within abdomen and even distant metastasis. [8] A tumour size of more than 7 cm, two or more mitotic figures per ten high power fields, necrosis, haemorrhage and marked nuclear atypia correlates adversely with prognosis and they have tendency to reccur and metastasise. [9] Determination of malignancy is considered the most essential factor to be assessed as malignant tumors constitute approximately 25–40% of cases. In their largest series of steroid cell tumors, Hayes and Scully have summarized the main histopathological features of malignancy including the presence of more than two mitotic figures per 10 high power fields in 92% of cases, necrosis in 86% of studies, a tumor size larger than 7 cm in 78%, hemorrhage and grade 2–3 atypia in 77% and 64% of cases respectively. In our case the diagnosis was confirmed as a benign due to the low mitotic

rate of less than 2/20 HPF and the mild atypia, in addition to the benign clinical behavior and the absence of metastatic lesions. [1]

Treatment decision depends on many prognostic factors including the stage of the tumor, the presence of malignant features, age of the patient, and fertility desire. In general, surgical resection is considered the main choice for benign steroid cell tumors. Therefore, unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy is highly recommended for women with fertility desire and low-stage disease as in our patient, whereas total hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy is mostly performed in postmenopausal women, as in our case. Furthermore, adjuvant chemotherapy should be applied to patients with malignant tumors. 90% of the cases are classified as stage I cancer according to the FIGO staging system. This female patient group is characterized by a positive prognosis after operational treatment, and the survival rate is estimated at 84-95%. [10]

The gold standard for treatment of these cases is hysterectomy with removal of the adnexa with comprehensive staging. If a woman in her reproductive period wishes to maintain her fertility, one side adnexectomy is also taken into account. Patients with stage IA-IC desiring to preserve their fertility could be treated by fertility-sparing surgery and lymphadenectomy can be skipped. In older women or patients at an advanced stage, removal of the uterus, ovaries, the omentum, and (to the extent possible) metastatic deposits is considered to be standard surgery. [11] In advanced cases a follow-up treatment is recommended either in the BEP combination (bleomycin + etoposide + cisplatin), VAC combination (vinblastine + doxorubicin + cisplatin) or paclitaxel/carboplatin. If the tumor relapses, recurrent surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and potentially hormone therapy is used. Patient surveillance and patient follow-up are crucial after the surgical treatment.

Conclusion

Although ovarian steroid cell tumours represent a rare category, they must be considered in the differential diagnosis for virilization symptoms due to the importance of early diagnosis and management.

References

1. Hayes MC, Scully RE. Ovarian steroid cell tumors (not otherwise specified). A clinic pathological analysis of 63 cases. *Am J Surg Pathol* 1987; 11:835-45.
2. Harris AC, Wakely PE, Kaplowitz PB Jr, Lovinger RD. Steroid cell tumour of the ovary in a child. *Archives of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine* 1991; 115:150-4.
3. Young RH, Shully RE. Steroid cell tumors of the ovary. In: Fox H, Wells M, eds. *Spain Obstetric and Gynecological Pathology*. Churchill Livingstone 2003:845-56.
4. Chun YJ, Choi HJ, Lee HN, et al. An asymptomatic ovarian steroid cell tumor with complete cystic morphology: a case report. *Obstet Gynecol Sci* 2013;56(1):50-5.
5. Rachon D. Differential diagnosis of hyperandrogenism in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Exp Clin Endocrinol Diabetes* 2012; 120:205-9.
6. Mehdi G, Ansari HA, Sherwani RK, et al. Ovarian steroid cell tumour: correlation of histopathology with clinicopathologic features. *Patholog Res Int* 2011; 2011:987895.
7. Tampakoudis P, Zafrakas M, Kostopoulou E, et al. Ovarian Sertoli-Leydig cell tumor with coexistent vaginal angiomyxoma: case report and review of the literature. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 2004; 25:116.
8. Scully RE. Tumours of the ovary— maldeveloped gonads. 2nd series. Fascicle 16. Washington, DC: Armed Forces Institute of Pathology 1982.
9. Russell P, Robboy SJ, Anderson MC. Sex cord-stromal and steroid cell tumors of the ovaries. Chap- 21. In: Robboy SJ, Anderson MC, Russell P, eds. *Pathology of the female reproductive tract*. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone 2002:607-40.
10. Markowska J, Mardas M. Sex cord stromal tumors of the ovary: principles of management. *Curr Gynecol Oncol* 2010; 8:265-72.
11. Ciebiera M, Baran A, Słabuszewska-Józwiak A, et al. Sertoli-Leydig cell tumour (SLCT)— the case of a 15 cm diameter ovarian tumour with negative markers and absent hormonal symptoms. *J Health Inequal* 2019; 5:117-9.